

WAYS OF EFFECTIVE ENERGY RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN HOUSING FUND SERVICES.

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Abstract. *This article examines issues related to the efficient use of energy resources in improving the quality of utility services.*

Keywords. *Green energy, smart technology, "Smart Energy," smart energy, energy-efficient.*

Introduction. The transition to an economy based on the efficient use of resources enables energy conservation. Revenues from energy resource savings are directed towards the technical and technological modernization of enterprises. It is possible to reduce production costs through the modernization of technologies and equipment, including increasing energy efficiency and ensuring uninterrupted energy supply. In turn, cost reduction ensures the competitiveness of products in domestic and foreign markets and stimulates structural changes. The widespread implementation of "green" standards in Uzbekistan, which contribute to production and resource conservation, will create a foundation for promoting our products in foreign markets and ensure the stability and competitiveness of the country's export potential.

Review of literature on the topic. We can observe that certain aspects of the housing and communal services management system have been studied in the research of domestic scientists. Specifically, the research of domestic scientists such as M.K. Ziyaev, R.I. Nurimbetov, V.U. Yodgorov, I.Kh. Davletov, O.Sh. Mamanazarov, T.A. Khasanov, R.R. Ortikova, D.Ya. Butunov, K.E. Rakhimov, and A.S. Sultanov reflects issues of housing stock management and improving the quality of housing and communal services.

Research Methodology. In the research process conducted for writing our scientific article, methods of scientific reasoning, abstract-logical thinking, comparative and systematic analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic approach, induction and deduction were employed.

Analysis and results. According to the analysis, the potential of solar and wind energy in our country is sufficient to cover the current electricity demand by 10-12 times. However, this enormous opportunity remained unutilized for many years. In recent years, the government has paid significant attention to this sector, creating a legal foundation. Large-scale programs for developing "green energy" sources have

been initiated. An attractive environment has been established for investors. To date, \$2.1 billion in foreign direct investment has been attracted to the industry, and projects worth an additional \$13 billion are being implemented. Modern solar and wind power plants are being constructed in almost all regions of the country.

In particular, 9 large solar and wind power plants with a total capacity of 1.6 gigawatts were put into operation in Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Samarkand, and Surkhandarya regions. Six large and small hydroelectric power stations with a total capacity of 183 megawatts were commissioned in Andijan, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, and Tashkent regions.

Additionally, solar panels with a total capacity of 457 megawatts have been installed at social facilities, enterprises and organizations, buildings belonging to entrepreneurs, and residential homes. Banks have allocated nearly 2 trillion soums in resources for these projects.

As a result, the potential to generate an additional 5 billion kilowatt-hours of environmentally clean electricity and save 1.5 billion cubic meters of gas has been created.

The comprehensive work in this field has also given a significant boost to increasing the production of transformers, various types of cables, heating collectors, solar panels, insulators, and metal poles at local enterprises.

In a word, "green" energy is becoming both one of the drivers of our economy and a truly nationwide movement.

Achieving resource efficiency in the energy sector contributes to changes in demand and the production of new types of products. The transition to "green energy" primarily stimulates the demand for innovative equipment and technologies. This is crucial for implementing "green" principles. On the other hand, the transition to new "green" norms and standards will positively impact the growth of consumer culture, lead to an increase in demand for energy-efficient goods, and result in changes in the structure of supply and demand. This ensures structural changes in the economy.

For this, first and foremost, it is advisable to reform the energy consumption accounting system. The current system only takes into account technical losses, while commercial losses are not recognized. This does not motivate energy companies to develop and implement a set of measures that would encourage them to reduce energy losses and improve energy efficiency. We consider it expedient to maintain records of commercial energy losses and develop plans for their systematic reduction. This is because reducing commercial losses of electricity in power grids is one of the most important factors in energy conservation and increasing the transmission capacity of electrical networks.

When considering energy conservation, rational use, and increasing energy efficiency in heat supply and utility companies, it is advisable to take into account the following:

- establishing maximum consumption norms for fuel and energy resources for equipment and machinery in operation at public utilities;
- managing centralized heat supply systems through a unified heat dispatch center;
- monitoring compliance with consumption regimes by heat supply enterprises and consumers;
- implementing quality indicators for thermal energy;
- fully installing heat energy (hot water) consumption measuring devices for consumers;
- implementing projects aimed at modernizing and reconstructing boiler houses, gradually decommissioning low-energy-efficiency boiler houses, and reducing fuel consumption for heat energy production;
- establishing norms for fuel and energy resource consumption per unit of output produced at heat supply and utility companies;
- attracting funds from international financial institutions, as well as foreign and domestic investors;
- retraining and improving the qualifications of managers and specialists.
- installation of a specialized heat supply system for buildings and structures when constructing a new complex comprising social facilities, private sector buildings, and newly built houses;
- disconnection of existing buildings and structures from the centralized heat supply system during major renovations in accordance with the requirements applicable to new buildings and structures.

Additionally, it is advisable to utilize automated "smart" technologies for energy conservation.

Specifically, the "Smart Energy" system by CSA (Connectivity Standards Alliance) can be implemented.

Smart Energy supports plans to meet the future energy, water, and gas needs of the utility ecosystem, manufacturers, and regulatory bodies. It facilitates the creation of more environmentally friendly homes by providing consumers with reliable information and necessary automation systems. This enables consumers to easily reduce their energy consumption and save money. Transparency of information and costs increases consumer confidence, allowing them to make more effective consumption decisions for the benefit of utilities and the environment. Utility companies, in turn, will have the opportunity to establish better control over network management.

Conclusion. Smart energy fundamentally changes consumer knowledge, enabling optimization of energy consumption, reduction of waste, and simplification of compliance with regulatory requirements.

Based on the above considerations, we can say that the use of energy-saving and smart technologies in the field of public utilities will serve to accelerate the development of not only the energy sector, but also the national economy in the future.

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